

SEMANTIC AMBIGUITY OF CAN IN WORD ASSOCIATIONS¹

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Abstract: *The present work tackles some issues about ambiguity in terms of homonymy. As a result of an experiment only two of the meanings of the word 'can' are in the focus here. The purpose of the article is to summarize the observations on word associations supplied by means of students' answers in a method very similar to a free association test. Regardless of the specific modal shades such as permission, ability, possibility, offer, etc. that this particular verb could carry and without having the purpose to give an exhaustive list of meanings, the test supplies information about the related words some of which can come into expressions. They are options of useful phrases that could be taught at school while making schoolchildren acquaintance with multiple meanings of the word 'can'. The test used in the experiment provides data which is compared to expressions from two corpora (BUY-BNC and Word Neighbors).*

Keywords: *ambiguity, foreign language, word associations.*

Introduction

Whether we should call it a conflict of homonyms as Cabanillas [1] or ambiguity, the so called clash between words of same phonemes and graphemes exists. Zhang et al [14] claim that universally words with more than one meaning prevail over those with just one. I would rather agree with Mamedova [6] who observes it to be especially true about the English language. Homonyms and polysemes are in this group of the so called "ambiguous words" [14].

The abundance of homonymy in the English language includes not only homophones but also homographs at the same time as it is the case with the word the present paper

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focuses on. According to Cambridge dictionary [17] online *can*, firstly as a modal verb, is used to express ability, permission, request, possibility, offer, then as a noun it designates “a closed metal container”; “the amount of food or drink that is contained in a can”; used as a slang word, it can mean “headphones”; in informal speech it stands for prison or even toilet. Another use of it as a verb is to “preserve food by putting it into a can or into a jar (= glass container) from which the air is removed”; in slang “If you get canned, you are dismissed from your job”. As it is clear, the word has different related meanings but also some of them are unrelated. Meanings of a word without any relation between them are generally referred to homonymy while polysemy concerns related senses. In our case some of the meanings can be recognized as a phenomenon of polysemy, others as homonymy. If the idea about both being placed in one and the same continuum is adopted here, the twofold classification would not be of great significance for the present research.

Frisson and Pickering [2] underline the controversy of views about representation of word meaning while focusing on two positions, one is “the *radical polysemy* view which maintains that all specific representations of a word are stored, and the *radical monosemy* view, which claims that the only one meaning of a word is stored and that specific interpretations are computed on the basis of contextual information...”. The importance of context is generally recognized. Nyysönen [8] explains that while “...the learning of lexical phrases starts with the commonest patterns in the commonest uses, the acquisition of lexical items begins with the commonest items in the commonest patterns, making it possible to learn and practice items and patterns in parallel from the start.”

Following the classification of Arnold (as cited in [6]) to “exactly homonyms, homophones and homographs”, *can* (as a modal verb and as a noun) could be defined as one of the first group, and as this group goes on to be further divided, it seems to match the subgroup of “Partial homonyms having the same initial form but different paradigms”. The plural form of *can* as a

noun needs –s to be added, while can as a modal verb does not add –s for present simple 3p. sg, so there wouldn't be any further kind of overlapping and the word remains on the lexical level of homonymy, escaping the grammatical one. If we were interested in can as a full verb, e.g. with the meaning of putting something into a can, it would be suitable for the group of Ginsburg' s lexico-grammatical homonyms (another classification as cited in [6]). Rothwell's Dictionary of homonyms [11] adds some more interesting uses of the word but the paper is organized around two of them – “the present tense of the verb ‘to be able’ and ‘a metallic cylindrical container which can contain a variety of products from various kinds of food to paint or beer’.

Method and participants

The work relies on two online corpora, i.e. Brigham Young University-British National Corpus (BYU-BNC) [15] and Word Neighbors (WN) [16]. The latter is developed by the Hong Kong University of Science and Technology. The search for appropriate data in BYU-BNC is not limited to particular register. It includes different kinds of texts both written and spoken, e.g. fiction/drama/prose/poetry, public debate, conversation, meeting, etc. WN offers a similar computer assisted processing of data. For the present study it is important that both corpora give information not only about frequency and word class but in addition, it is easy to check the context and decide whether any of the examples are suitable for the purpose.

The results from the corpora are compared with the findings from a very similar to free association test. The associations data is gathered in a period of approximately three successive years. The informants are 29 undergraduate students of Primary school pedagogy and foreign language. Their age varies from 20 to 42. The procedure is the same as depicted in an earlier work [4]. As it included 20 stimulus words and the reaction words were analyzed only for part of the stimuli there, some of the left out data is included here together with the results from the same experiment conducted in the following two years.

Results and discussion

Although the difference is clear-cut with some homonymous words, others do not offer such an obvious distinction ([9] and [13]) or as Restu [9] suggests the interpretation seems to be a matter of subjectivity. As word frequency is an important prerequisite for language processing [12], a corpus research appears useful to decide which meaning is more commonly used in language. WN classifies them as in figure 1:

Figure 1. Number of occurrences of the word *can* for the different word classes according to Word Neighbors

The authors warn of possible mistakes in terms of word classes as the results are received by computer program work. There were a few instances indeed such as "...who was found stuffed in a garbage can in a Luanda suburb", where *can* was classified as a verb, but the context supplied enough information to have good reasons to reorganize the data. After more or less subjective reconsidering of the examples, the final results did not lead to unexpected twist as the group of verbs remained the largest of all.

Although the numbers are different and the sources vary, the proportions of the verbs compared to nouns usage in BUY-BNC lead to the same conclusion (see fig. 2 and fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Number of occurrences of can as a verb (can_v search) according to BYU-BNC

Fig. 3. Number of occurrences of can as a noun (can_n search) according to BYU-BNC

The next figure shows some of the most frequent words that follow the verb can in BUY-BNC.

Fig. 4. Frequency collocations of the verb can in BUY-BNC

A detailed summary of the most frequently used collocations lists words like watering, empty, recycling, opener, equal, tomatoes, tin, collection, etc. as part of the expressions with can as a noun.

they show a deeper level of language acquisition. But the syntagmatic associations were the ones that draw a connective line between the results from the test and the corpora data. A close comparison showed the co-occurrence with all of the response words for can as a noun. Unfortunately they were not used in collocations. The only coincidence was the co-occurrence of metal and can as a noun. After reconsidering the examples in context only 3 of the suggested in BYU-BNC were found appropriate, and two in WN. The substance characteristic appeared to be the common link between word – associations – collocation. Synonyms of metal were present in both corpora as collocations with aluminium and with tin. The response word rubbish was another case which was difficult to be found as a collocation with can as a noun. In British English the more natural collocation would be rubbish bin, and its synonym garbage is preferred by Americans while adding + decomposability characteristics. It appeared in 13 examples in BYU-BNC and there were 51 garbage can/ cans examples in WN.

The top 20 collocations with can as a verb showed insignificant overlap with the reaction words provided by the informants. The opposition can – can't was the strongest for all of the sources used in the research. The variety of suggested verbs as a reaction to the stimulus word can differed from the top ten collocations except for the verb help. In search of free associations, a student retrieved a well stored social expression in her mind.

According to Storkel and Maekawa [12] “learning a secondary meaning of a homonym differs fundamentally from learning a novel word.” While exploring the way semantic similarity affects ambiguous word learning in second language, Zhang et al [14] suggest that there might be different mechanisms that participate in learning L2 homonyms and polysemes. Their results give evidence that the first meaning may have a negative impact on learning the second meaning of homonyms (the “interference effect”), while with polysemes it seems to be the other way round. The first meaning of

polysemous words may help to learn the second one (the “facilitation effect”).

As a matter of fact it is difficult to decide which of the two uses of can appears earlier in terms of acquisition. On the one hand, can as a verb occurs in all English language primary school textbooks in Bulgaria. On the other hand, the noun is well-known even to pre-school children. In this case it is a loan word entangled in everyday Bulgarian language to such an extent that at least children would not most probably connect it to foreign words at all. Such a complication is possibly due to the capacity of language as it is appropriately referred to “the primary means of cultural transmission ...” [5].

As Rodd et al [10] put it “learning a new word meaning might be particularly challenging for children if they already have a different, semantically unrelated meaning associated with that word”. Storkel and Maekawa [12] share the two possibilities viewed by different authors concerning the comparison of acquisition in terms of easiness in learning completely new words and once well-known homophones appearing with a new meaning. Shortly, some consider it easier to learn unfamiliar words due to the human mind “preference for unique mapping” as what concerns lexical and semantic representations, others share the other way round supporting the view that homonyms are learned more rapidly since there is less new information to deal with.

In Bulgarian ‘kenche’ is a noun. It is a loan word with a Bulgarian diminutive suffix added to it used as a slang word. It is widespread in colloquial language and probably even most small children are familiar with it. If we adopt the view that foreign (second) language acquisition resembles the way children learn their mother tongue, Goldfield’s experiment results [3] that children produce more nouns than verbs (but they comprehend more verbs than they use, though) would definitely recognize the leading role of can as a noun. But McDonough et al [7] notice the rise of opposition to such a view worldwide and suggest a better explanation about the difference between noun and verb acquisition as due to “a

word's imageability". They state that the higher the imageability of the word, the easier it is to be learnt despite the type of word class they belong to.

Therefore, the expected results from the experiment were to have more reaction words to the stimulus word as a noun. The surprising 84 per cent of all acceptable reaction words were a response to the word as a verb. In case can as a verb is used in positive short answer of Yes/No- questions we have the same vowel sound as in the noun and the homonyms are both homophones and homographs, but in other cases, e.g. in general questions where can is in unstressed position and the vowel is reduced to schwa, we can talk only about homographs. This means that context would reduce ambiguity. But the problem remains as free association tests are conducted with stimuli out of any context.

Conclusions and further work

In terms of chronology, most probably the first acquired of the two meanings is the word as a noun. Later in school education with the start of language learning, a new meaning – that of the modal verb – is added to the elements of the developing language map in students' mind. This is the crucial point when the ambiguity could take place.

The research shows overall discrepancy or insignificant overlap of response words in a free association test with collocations in the two corpora. As it was already underlined, the different nature of associations and collocations is not neglected. Yet a parallel could be drawn between the two that would probably facilitate the process of foreign language learning. In other words, the lack of coincidence of words might be interpreted as a sign of the necessity to teach ready to use structures. They could be related to syntagmatic associations, since the latter are said to be typical for children's associations.

In future studies, it may be a starting point for a new research of students who are future pre/ primary school teachers. The findings of the present research could be used in developing an English lesson based on the semantic links

between the words. It could include the reaction words as well as some of the most frequent collocations.

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